

THE ROLE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING STRATEGIES

Kushakova Shakhzodakhon Dilshod qizi

Fergana state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6838972>

Abstract. Youth education is one of the most significant and critical challenges confronting the country today. The science of pedagogy is the major tool in training young people for such a critical field as future personnel. The author covers in full the latest educational technologies employed in science today and their significance in this essay.

Keywords: pedagogical technologies, teachers, students, development of education, teaching strategies and etc.

РОЛЬ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ СТРАТЕГИЯХ

Аннотация. Воспитание молодежи является одной из самых значительных и острых проблем, стоящих перед страной сегодня. Педагогическая наука является важнейшим инструментом в подготовке молодежи для такой важной области, как будущие кадры. В этом эссе автор полностью освещает новейшие образовательные технологии, используемые сегодня в науке, и их значение.

Ключевые слова: педагогические технологии, учителя, ученики, развитие образования, стратегии обучения и др.

INTRODUCTION

In many ways, teaching activities are related with expanding his professional prestige, as is the progressive and successful implementation of our country's national training program. In specialist training, the teacher is a specific socio-political figure who must meet educational and personal qualifications. As a result, the teacher is committed to the concept of independence, has well-developed scientific thinking and knowledge of the profession, and has a deep knowledge of the subject, is a master of pedagogical communication, pedagogical-psychological and methodological knowledge and skills, and can quickly solve various pedagogical tasks, perceive, study, and evaluate situations. It should also be able to identify the most relevant techniques and means of display.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We believe that the basic foundation of pedagogical technology is the technology chosen by the teacher and student to obtain a guaranteed outcome from the specified objective, that is, to accomplish a guaranteed result on the aim in the sphere of teaching. Each educational technology employed can foster a collaborative activity between teacher and student; both can benefit if students can think independently and creatively during the learning process. If they can search, analyze, draw their own conclusions, evaluate themselves, the group, and the group, and the teacher can create opportunities and conditions for such activities, we believe that each lesson, topic, and subject has its own technology, that is, pedagogical technology in the learning process is an individual process, which the teacher can create opportunities and conditions for.

Every science teacher's job is to plan meaningful lessons in order to educate a harmoniously developed generation. Such pedagogical technologies are also quite useful in history lectures. Because it is not possible to question each student the topic in 45 minutes, we

can use other approaches to determine how well the student understands the material. To accomplish this, we can incorporate this pedagogical technology or method into our class, taking into account the topic and the student's age. The student is expected to learn the names, dates, and historical terminology of more historical personalities in history classes, and we must pay special attention to these in each subject.

Existing educational technologies are classified into kinds based on a variety of criteria. Before delving into these characteristics, it should be emphasized that pedagogical technology is always complicated, employing more than one aspect, approach, or principle. That is, technologies that are specific to the following classes do not exist. However, because each pedagogical technology focuses on one or more aspects of the educational process, they are classified according to these qualities. The relationship between educational content and interactive approaches. Thus, we have proposed an integrated strategy that highlights the first crucial criterion for better teaching method selection, systematization, and application in the practice of learning process planning. Criteria for the selection of traditional methods in pedagogy have been developed in large numbers, and in recent years in the works of didactic scholars more than twenty of them are cited.

RESULTS

Similarly, there is some evidence that blogging assists kids in learning independently while simultaneously gaining intercultural understanding and linguistic skills. They not only enhance their writing skills, but they also gain an awareness of the culture of the target language. Language teachers should refresh their abilities by receiving training in the use of technology in the language-learning classroom, such as computers, multimedia, and smart boards. Instructors can also encourage their pupils to use technology for language acquisition; the Internet, in particular, can be beneficial for self-directed study.

Because pedagogical technology is subjective in nature, each educator must creatively organize the process of education and rearing based on their abilities and professional capabilities. Pedagogical technologies, regardless of their shape, method, or mode of organization:

- ✓ increasing the effectiveness of pedagogical activities;
- ✓ decision of interaction between teachers and students;
- ✓ Ensuring that students acquire a thorough knowledge of the subject;
- ✓ Development of independent, free and creative thinking skills in students;
- ✓ create the necessary conditions for students to realize their potential.

DISCUSSION

Modern educational technology are considered as a tool of realizing a new educational paradigm. The most general understanding of the phrase "technology" is that it reflects a scientifically and practically grounded system of activity that is implemented by man for the purpose of environmental transformation.

Technology has brought about revolutionary changes in all aspects of society, including interpersonal communication, the economics, the entertainment sector, and even education. Students appear to be confronted with changes that not only profoundly alter the way they learn, but also their daily lives, now more than ever. It is simply impossible to ignore the tremendous impact that modern technologies have on new generations of students. Educational technology

refers to the implementation of advanced technologies, i.e. software and hardware that enable modern teaching methods.

CONCLUSIONS

As a result, students and instructors have access to a plethora of digital and instructional tools that encourage mutual cooperation and help students master the teaching material. This modern method has influenced education at all levels, from elementary school to college. Improving the learning experience is strongly tied to the demands and habits of students. Children expect information to be delivered in a similar manner at school because they utilize social media, the Internet, and video games on a daily basis. Lesson content should be graphic and interesting, capturing their attention and containing as little duplicate information as possible, which is one of the traditional method to education's key flaws. Of course, school responsibilities are not the same as playing video games, but it is useful to know what things can draw and hold students' attention and help them master the teaching material.

REFERENCES

1. Kelsen B. Teaching EFL to the I-generation: A Survey of Using YouTube as Supplementary Material with College EFL Students in Taiwan. - Indonesia, CALL-EJ, 2009. - P. 35.
2. National Program of Personnel Training of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2000 y
3. A. Askarova, M. Khayitbaev” Pedagogy " T., "Suggestion" 2008 y
4. Levine A., Ferenz O., Reves T. EFL Academic Reading and Modern Technology: How Can We Turn Our Students into Independent Critical Readers. -London: TESL-EJ, 2000. - P. 312.
5. Ramachandran S. Integrating New Technologies into Language Teaching: Two Activities for EAP Classroom. - Canada, TESL Canada Journal / Revue TESL du Canada, 2004. - P. 215.